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RDA and Microsoft White Paper

From HPC to Quantum-
Shaping the Future of
Research Computing

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Based on the RDA-Microsoft roundtables June 2025

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- 1. Executive Summary 4
- 2. Introduction & Background to the Roundtables 5
 - 2.1 High Performance Computing (HPC) to Quantum the future of research computing: Rationale and Global Stakeholder Input 6
 - 2.2 Participant Profiles and HPC & Quantum Experience 8
- 3. Global Thought Leadership: Expert Keynotes and Audience Discussions 9
 - 3.1 Building the Future of High-Performance Computing by a Synergistic Inclusion of Quantum Acceleration 10
 - Audience Q and A with Mikael Johansson: Highlights 11
 - 3.2 Human Boundaries for High Performance Computing 12
 - Audience Q and A with Sabina Leonelli: Highlights 13
 - 3.3 Accelerating Discovery: High Performance Computing for the Next Generation of Research 14
 - Audience Q and A with Torsten Bloth: Highlights 15
 - 3.4 Quantum Supercomputing from a Supercomputing Centre’s Perspective 15
 - Audience Q and A with Pascal Elahi: Highlights 16
 - 3.5 Transforming R&D with advanced HPC and AI towards Quantum 17
 - Q&A with Naoyuki Isogai: Highlights 18
 - 3.6 Quantum Horizons: Practical Progress and Future Directions 19
 - Audience Q and A with Ujjwal Kumar: Highlights 20
- 4. Breakout Dialogues on HPC and Quantum: Insights into Applications, Barriers, Enablers, Skills and Policy 21
 - 4.1 June 3 Breakout Sessions: Data, Cloud Access, Quantum skills, Security 21
 - 4.2 June 5: High impact Use cases, Quantum readiness, Equity, Ethics 23
 - Cross cutting and Shared Themes 26
- 5 Key Findings and Recommendations 26
 - 5.1 Better Together: The Quantum +HPC+AI Advantage 27
 - 5.2 Democratising HPC and Quantum Infrastructure: Cloud a Key Enabler 28
 - 5.3 Post quantum Security: No Time to Wait 29
 - 5.4 Ethics by Design: Proactive and Multi stakeholder Approach for Quantum & AI .. 30

5.5. Bridging the Quantum and HPC Skills Gap through Education and Inclusion	31
6. Final Reflection	33
About the Research Data Alliance.....	33
About Microsoft	33
Acknowledgments	34
Annex A: Keynote Speaker Bios	35
Torsten Bloth, HPC and AI Black Belt EMEA, Microsoft, Berlin, Germany.....	35
Pascal Elahi, Quantum Supercomputing Lead, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, Perth, Australia	35
Naoyuki Isogai, Asia Regional Head for Cloud Solutions HPC/AI, Microsoft Corporation, Taiwan	36
Mikael Johansson, Manager, Quantum Technologies, CSC, Espoo, Finland	36
Ujjwal Kumar, Principal Architect, Office of CTO, Microsoft Asia, Singapore	37
Sabina Leonelli, Professor of Philosophy of Technology, Technische Universität München, Germany	37
Annex B: Contributing Participants.....	38

1. Executive Summary

Quantum computing, High-Performance Computing (**HPC**), and Artificial Intelligence (**AI**) are forming the backbone of a new era in scientific discovery. To explore the implications of these innovative technology on research, the **Research Data Alliance (RDA)** and **Microsoft** organised two global expert roundtables in June 2025 on the topic of “**From HPC to Quantum – Shaping the future of research computing**”. Through expert keynote speeches and in-depth breakout discussions, researchers, technologists, policy leaders and funders from over **22 countries** examined how quantum and HPC are applied in practice, where the most pressing challenges lie, and what actions are needed to ensure these technologies deliver broad and equitable benefit.

The roundtables revealed that **hybrid computational models** are already emerging, where HPC manages scale, AI accelerates insight, and quantum offers precision for targeted problems. Despite expanding **access via cloud platforms**, structural barriers persist: inadequate connectivity, skills gaps, fragile governance frameworks, and looming security threats posed by quantum-capable decryption. Based on the insights we present the following **findings and recommendations** for global research stakeholders:

- Invest in hybrid **HPC, AI, and quantum infrastructure** through integrated testbeds and unified, user-friendly software platforms to accelerate discovery.
- **Democratise** access to advanced computing through **cloud computing** while addressing **the global internet connectivity gap**
- Accelerate the adoption of **post-quantum cryptography standards** and build institutional "**crypto-agility**" to counter the security threat related to quantum advancement
- Form multi-stakeholder teams to consider the **societal implications** of HPC and quantum projects and embed **diverse perspectives** by design.
- Bridge the talent gap by integrating **quantum and HPC fundamentals and ethics** into STEM curricula, expanding interdisciplinary training, and developing user-friendly tools to lower barriers for researchers.

We hope that these findings offer strategic guidance for research institutions, governments, funders, and technology providers to collectively shape a future where research computing is not only more **impactful** but also **equitable, secure, and ethically aligned**.

2. Introduction & Background to the Roundtables

Rapidly advancing technologies, notably Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Quantum Computing, are significantly impacting the landscape of scientific research. From reducing chemical discovery timelines (from several months down to approximately 200 hours¹) to accelerating the understanding of protein structures, (an advancement recognised²), the impact and potential of these technologies is immense^{3,4}.

In recognition of these advancements and their implications, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and Microsoft jointly organised a series of expert roundtables in May and June 2025. These roundtables aimed to stimulate global community dialogue, foster meaningful discussions, and identify practical frameworks and best practices for responsible advancement in the impactful fields of AI and Quantum Computing.

The two main themes of the roundtables were:

- "Data Readiness and Data Centric AI Skills." (2025, 13 and 15 May)
- "From HPC to Quantum Shaping the Future of Research Computing" (2025, 3 and 5 June)

The roundtables were structured to maximise global engagement and inclusive dialogue. Sessions were scheduled to accommodate participants across diverse time zones, ensuring broad international participation. The tangible outcomes of these sessions are two whitepapers, one per theme, made openly available to the global research community in July 2025. This white paper synthesises findings specifically from the two sessions that concentrated on "From HPC to Quantum Shaping the Future of Research Computing."

To gather valuable insights for the roundtables RDA leveraged its position as an inclusive and open discussion platform, with a global community presence across all continents, and experience in data driven innovation. Concurrently, Microsoft contributed its expansive technological expertise, and its technology driven global research initiatives. In April 2025 Microsoft joined the RDA as an organisational member. You can consult the organisational profiles of the RDA and Microsoft at the end of **Section 6** of this document.

Invited attendees at the roundtables included leading researchers, policymakers, funders, data stewards, technologists, and industry leaders. By engaging both public and private sector partners, these dialogues aimed to foster a constructive discussion among stakeholders who are driving the advancements and usage of these technologies.

2.1 High Performance Computing (HPC) to Quantum the future of research computing: Rationale and Global Stakeholder Input

High Performance Computing (HPC) and quantum technologies are reaching a critical inflection point. HPC is now indispensable to large scale scientific research, while quantum computing is shifting from theoretical potential to early-stage application.

Recent developments illustrate accelerating momentum across both industry and national strategies. On the industry side, Google's Willow processor¹, AWS's Ocelot chip² Microsoft's Majorana 1³, continues to push toward scalable, error reduced, fault tolerant quantum systems. Among governments and policy initiatives across the world, **Europe's EuroHPC Joint Undertaking**⁴ has committed over €7 billion to build exascale class infrastructure and explore HPC quantum integration. The **United States**, under the **National Quantum Initiative**⁵, has invested across several national funding, standards, and administrative bodies with plans to scale further under the Department of Energy Quantum Leadership Act of 2025⁶. **Australia's National Quantum Strategy**⁷ commits public and private capital toward infrastructure, commercialisation, and workforce development. Meanwhile, **China** has invested heavily in quantum networks and secured satellite-based quantum communication capabilities⁸, demonstrating a strategic push to lead in quantum and post quantum technologies.

Together, these developments reflect a growing global consensus that high performance computing, quantum systems, and robust data infrastructure are essential to future scientific leadership, economic resilience, and technological sovereignty. As data generation accelerates across fields such as climate science, genomics, and artificial intelligence, the ability to store, process, and interpret large scale data will increasingly rely on advanced computing. HPC and quantum technologies are not only enablers of scientific discovery but also foundational to data driven innovation and competitiveness.

Acknowledging this momentum, the RDA Microsoft roundtables were created to convene the international research community at a pivotal moment in the HPC and quantum progression.

¹ <https://blog.google/technology/research/google-willow-quantum-chip/>

² <https://www.aboutamazon.com/news/aws/quantum-computing-aws-ocelot-chip>

³ <https://news.microsoft.com/azure-quantum/>

⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/high-performance-computing-joint-undertaking>

⁵ <https://www.quantum.gov/>

⁶ <https://www.congress.gov/bills/119/congress-119/senate/bills/579/text>

⁷ <https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/national-quantum-strategy>

⁸ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2472766-quantum-satellite-sets-globe-spanning-distance-record/>

Figure 1: Top discussion themes preferences of the participants at the time of registration across both roundtables.

To ensure the roundtable sessions addressed relevant priorities, participants were consulted in advance to identify preferred thematic areas. While not all registrants were able to join the live sessions due to format and scheduling limitations, their input was instrumental in shaping the agenda. Through the registration process, over 130 participants from more than 30 countries expressed interest in contributing to discussions on skills and policy, and the challenges of transitioning from HPC to quantum computing as shown in Figure 1. The keynote speeches and subsequent breakout sessions of the roundtables reflected these thematic priorities. In the next section, we describe the profiles of participants who took part in the live roundtable discussions, offering a closer look at their backgrounds, roles, and levels of engagement with HPC and quantum technologies.

2.2 Participant Profiles and HPC & Quantum Experience

The roundtables convened strategically diverse stakeholders from the global research and technology community. Participants represented academic researchers, national infrastructure leaders, technical architects, and policy advisors across the two roundtable sessions, a total of **47 participants** representing **22 countries** contributed to the discussion. The **June 3** session included participants from **Finland, Canada, United States, Sweden, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Estonia, France, Germany, Belgium, Ireland, Italy, South Africa, and India**. The June 5 session drew participants from **Australia, Netherlands, Germany, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Pakistan, Nepal, Indonesia, United Kingdom, India, Italy, Belgium, Taiwan, and the United States**. All the contributing participants who agreed to be acknowledged in this paper are listed in [Annex B](#). We thank them for their valuable contributions and discussions.

Figure 2: Participant HPC experience levels across the two round table sessions

To gain an understanding of participant experiences in the topics of the roundtable roundtables, we surveyed them in both sessions via live MentiMeter polls about their experience with HPC and Quantum Computing. As shown in Figure 2, most participants were already familiar with HPC, though not all were directly involved in its use.

With regards to the Quantum Computing experience as shown in Figure 3, a small subset of participants reported direct engagement, while most positioned themselves at a more exploratory stage.

Figure 3: Participant HPC experience levels across the two round table sessions

Beyond the self-reporting, when asked to describe quantum computing in three words, participants shared terms such as *innovative*, *exciting*, *fascinating*, as well as *complex*, *science fiction*, and *specialised*. The responses suggested broad enthusiasm and optimism about quantum’s potential. At the same time, for most participants, it remained an aspirational and futuristic concept.

Against this backdrop, the roundtables brought in global thought leaders to deepen the conversation, offer strategic framing, and explore what readiness for quantum and advanced computing could look like in practice. The following section brings together the summaries of the keynote speeches across the roundtables.

3. Global Thought Leadership: Expert Keynotes and Audience Discussions

This section presents key insights from global experts delivered during the RDA Microsoft roundtables on HPC and quantum technologies. It distills the central messages from each expert speaker and includes selected highlights from the audience Q&A sessions. Speaker biographies are provided in [Annex A](#).

3.1 Building the Future of High-Performance Computing by a Synergistic Inclusion of Quantum Acceleration

Speaker: Mikael Johansson, Manager, Quantum Technologies, CSC⁹, Espoo, Finland 2025, June 3

Mikael kicked off the roundtable keynotes with a clear message that quantum computers are fundamentally different from classical systems, not faster versions of them. Classical computers are deterministic and stable, producing the same result on each run. Quantum systems, by contrast, exploit physical principles like **superposition, entanglement, and interference**, and operate in a **probabilistic** and error prone manner.

Because of this, Mikael stressed the importance of rethinking problem formulation when using quantum systems. Classical programs cannot simply be recompiled for quantum hardware. Instead, problems must be restructured from the ground up, often aligning with quantum native methods such as matrix inversion or state preparation. Quantum computers are particularly promising for problems in quantum chemistry, materials science, pharmaceuticals, financial modelling, and complex optimisation.

At the systems level, Mikael argued that HPC centres are well positioned to support the early adoption of quantum computing. They already maintain the necessary infrastructure such as secure user authentication, resource scheduling, and technical support, that can be extended to manage quantum hardware.

Mikael highlighted that real value of future promise of Quantum may already be unlocked through targeted hybrid workflows combining classical High Performance Computing and Quantum Computing (QC) powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI). These include:

- Electronic structure calculations for applications in drug discovery, materials science, and quantum chemistry.
- Computational fluid dynamics (CFD), where quantum acceleration may benefit subroutines such as solving large linear systems.
- Risk modelling and portfolio optimisation in finance, where even modest improvements can offer major economic value.
- ML is already essential for pre and post processing, from quantum algorithm compilation to error mitigation and correction.

⁹ <https://csc.fi/en/>

- Quantum machine learning could enable models to train with fewer data points or escape classical local minima, where benefits extend beyond mere speed.
- Hybrid AI Quantum Computing (QC) systems could support digital twins and next generation climate models, particularly by simulating complex components like atmospheric chemistry, which are currently excluded from classical workflows due to computational cost.

"A Quantum Computer is not the next version of a supercomputer. To truly benefit from the quantum advantage in the short-term we need a hybrid approach. The combination of HPC+AI+QC is the most promising way forward. We need to start experimenting and engaging researchers across disciplines."

- Mikael Johansson

Audience Q and A with Mikael Johansson: Highlights

On how quantum machine learning differs from classical approaches: Mikael explained that quantum programs inherently operate differently from classical software, often requiring novel algorithmic design. For instance, methods like quantum reservoir computing represent entirely new approaches for uncovering patterns in data¹⁰. However, Johansson also reassured attendees that user friendly libraries and frameworks are emerging, which reduce the need for users to program directly at the qubit level.

On reproducibility and probabilistic outputs: Mikael acknowledged that quantum systems will not always return the same output, even when given identical inputs, due to their probabilistic nature. However, this does not equate to randomness. Instead, multiple runs of a quantum program can be used to generate a statistical distribution of outcomes, allowing researchers to identify the most probable and robust solutions. In that sense, reproducibility in quantum computing becomes a matter of statistical reliability rather than deterministic exactness.

On accessibility and hybrid system complexity: Mikael noted that while many quantum programming tools are built on familiar languages like Python, accessibility remains a significant challenge. Easing user adoption requires deliberate efforts: simplified programming environments, onboarding support, and clear guidance on how to apply quantum solutions to real problems. Hybrid systems do not, by themselves, make quantum computing easier to use; rather, they require continued investment in education and infrastructure to lower the barrier for researchers and practitioners.

¹⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41534-023-00734-4>

3.2 Human Boundaries for High Performance Computing

Speaker: Sabina Leonelli, Professor of Philosophy of Technology, Technische Universität München, Germany

2025, June 3

Sabina Leonelli examined the social, ethical, and institutional boundaries shaping how High Performance Computing (HPC) and quantum technologies are developed and used. Her speech focused on the challenge of ensuring these tools serve meaningful, equitable, and public interest goals.

She raised concerns about how the promise of acceleration and predictive power especially through digital twins enabled by HPC is often pursued without building adequate connections with domain expertise, local contexts, or long term societal needs. This disconnect, she argued, widens the gap between computational development and social usability.

Sabina stressed that systems like HPC and quantum simulations depend on more than data: they involve assumptions embedded through modelling, calibration, coding, and maintenance. She questioned how digital twins are currently “twinned” with the real world, noting a trend of adapting data to fit technical constraints rather than designing tools around contextual and societal needs.

She further outlined key challenges that limit the accessibility and accountability of current HPC systems:

- Technical inertia and interoperability gaps, especially with legacy software and hardware like sensors or meteorological systems.
- High infrastructure costs, which concentrate HPC access among well resourced institutions and regions.
- Difficulty translating domain specific tools, many of which are designed for CPU systems, into newer GPU or quantum environments.
- Rising energy demands, compounded by underdeveloped strategies for system maintenance and sustainability.
- Opacity in data provenance and governance, which threatens public trust and undermines informed decision making.

Sabina elaborated these challenges using the example of medical diagnostics, for instance, predictive models for pancreatic cancer may generate risk profiles, but offer little clinical utility when early screening and treatment infrastructure is lacking. In such cases, the promise of advanced computing may outpace healthcare systems’ ability to

respond, increasing disparities between those who can act on predictions and those who cannot.

Sabina called for more inclusive governance and capacity building, especially for researchers and practitioners in under resourced regions. She pointed to long standing efforts in the Research Data Alliance to create inclusive communities that consider social relevance, not just technical performance.

"We keep talking about (HPC/Quantum) acceleration, but if we don't bring diverse stakeholders and communities into the design process, we're just widening the gap between what computation can do and what society actually needs because technologists alone don't have all the answers."

- Sabina Leonelli

Audience Q and A with Sabina Leonelli: Highlights

On practical efforts to address inequality and equity in HPC: Sabina pointed to initiatives in Italy where digital twin projects are meant to serve the public, such as in urban planning and mobility. However, she noted a lack of genuine community engagement. Despite good intentions, there are few mechanisms for involving local stakeholders, such as taxi drivers or urban workers in shaping these tools. Without such input, projects risk reinforcing top-down assumptions while losing trust and practical relevance.

On citizen-oriented programming and low code access to HPC: Responding to a question about citizen access to HPC systems or low code platforms, Sabina admitted that she had not seen widespread adoption. Even in well-funded environments, demand from public agencies and large companies often overwhelms HPC facilities, leaving little room for startups, NGOs, or small research teams. Skills gaps and scale thresholds further limit who can meaningfully engage. As a result, early exposure to HPC use cases is often reserved for privileged institutions.

On the ethical framing of emerging technologies: Sabina argued that treating ethics as a checklist or compliance step is insufficient. Ethics should be seen as a form of reasoning embedded in scientific practice, not just a set of principles. She warned against offloading moral responsibility to AI or automation and called for building educational and institutional structures that support careful, long-term thinking about social impacts.

3.3 Accelerating Discovery: High Performance Computing for the Next Generation of Research

Speaker: Torsten Bloth, HPC and AI Black Belt EMEA, Microsoft, Berlin, Germany
2025, June 3

Torsten Bloth from Microsoft offered a sweeping overview of how cloud-based High-Performance Computing (HPC) is evolving to support modern science and innovation. With over two decades of experience in the HPC ecosystem, he framed Microsoft Azure not simply as a cloud platform, but as a purpose built HPC environment designed to meet the demands of research at scale.

He began by tracing the evolution of accelerated computing, from the CDC 6600 in 1964, through the rise of cluster computing in the 1990s, to the exascale era inaugurated by machines like Frontier in 2021. Alongside CPUs and GPUs, the architecture now increasingly includes quantum processors (QPUs), enabling radically different types of workloads to be executed efficiently and accurately.

Torsten highlighted the role of hybrid computing models, where cloud native workflows integrate classical HPC, AI, and quantum systems for faster and more refined results. He explained that Azure's infrastructure allows researchers to choose and combine these tools, offering flexibility that is rarely feasible in on-premise systems.

He underscored Microsoft's investment in building internal and external HPC capabilities, including purpose-built data centers and infrastructure partnerships. A case study from the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory illustrated these ideas in action. By combining HPC, AI, and Azure Quantum, the lab accelerated the discovery of new battery materials from months or years to just weeks, demonstrating the transformative potential of this integrated approach which was also stressed by his colleague Naoyuki Isogai in the June 5 session.

In closing, Torsten argued that cloud HPC is not just about speed or scale; it is about broadening access. By removing barriers like hardware provisioning and data silos, it empowers researchers across disciplines and geographies to tackle complex problems with cutting edge tools.

"By combining classical supercomputing, AI, and quantum computing within flexible cloud infrastructures, we enable researchers and innovators to work faster, scale better, and access cutting-edge tools without traditional barriers"

- Torsten Bloth

Audience Q and A with Torsten Bloth: Highlights

On whether quantum computing reduces data needs: Torsten clarified that a clear trend is already visible in classical HPC: AI techniques are successfully being used to reduce both the data volume and simulation time in fields like computational fluid dynamics. This involves training models on the outputs of expensive simulations to create fast surrogates, potentially reducing future workloads.

On AI's role in accelerating simulations: Torsten emphasised that applying AI to classical HPC problems is already proving valuable in reducing time to solution. He suggested that this logic could extend to hybrid quantum classical approaches as well, particularly when the goal is to lower computational cost and improve environmental efficiency.

3.4 Quantum Supercomputing from a Supercomputing Centre's Perspective

Speaker: Dr Pascal Jahan Elahi, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, 5 June 2025

Dr Pascal Elahi outlined the current challenges, opportunities, and future potential of quantum computing from the perspective of a national supercomputing centre. He opened his speech by reinforcing the conceptual distinctions between classical and quantum computing, building on Mikael Johansson's overview from the [June 3 session](#). Rather than replacing classical computing systems, Elahi emphasised that quantum computing introduces new possibilities for tackling complex scientific problems that are intractable using the current computing methods.

However, the capabilities of currently available quantum hardware remain limited. Devices are still at the foundation implementation level known as Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum (NISQ)¹¹. Current quantum systems require frequent calibration, and achieve only moderate gate fidelity. They require highly specialised operating environments, making it difficult to deploy within standard datacentre or HPC infrastructures. Another key challenge lies in rethinking how problems are defined and modelled at the hardware level. Programming for quantum systems often involves aligning problem structures directly with the underlying physics, rather than adapting existing classical code.

¹¹ <https://quantum.microsoft.com/en-us/insights/education/concepts/quantum-computing-implementation-levels>

Most future scenarios for both NISQ devices and fault tolerant quantum computers anticipate hybrid workflows, where quantum, classical, and accelerated computing systems operate together. Examples include IBM and Pasqal's¹² work on quantum centric supercomputers and the development of QPU (Quantum Processing Unit) focused datacentres at Israel's national Quantum Computing Centers¹³.

In a similar direction, the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre, where Dr Pascal Elahi serves as Quantum Lead, established the Quantum SUPERcomputing Innovation Hub to promote quantum innovation, education, and access.

One of the Hub's major milestones is the deployment of a room temperature quantum computer, developed by Quantum Brilliance, inside Pawsey's operational HPC environment¹⁴. This is the first deployment of its kind globally. In terms of educational and outreach they support, Quantum Girls, a school level programme to help develop the next generation of diverse and inclusive quantum researchers.

"This is a really exciting time to be involved (in quantum). It's about democratising access. That's how we get to quantum utility: solutions that might be faster, cheaper, more energy efficient. We don't know the full potential of quantum, and that's exactly why we need more people trying."

- Pascal Elahi

Audience Q and A with Pascal Elahi: Highlights

On democratising access and hardware diversity of quantum computers: Pascal highlighted that not all quantum hardware is alike, and different systems are better suited to different algorithms or gate structures. Broadening access, including through cloud platforms like AWS Braket, allows researchers to trial diverse technologies and avoid getting "stuck" with underperforming hardware. "Democratising access can only help," he noted.

On accessing quantum resources at Pawsey supercomputing centre: Pascal explained that quantum access at Pawsey will mirror the existing national HPC merit allocation process. Researchers propose a scientific problem, specify computational needs, and are evaluated by technical and scientific review panels¹⁵. He

¹² <https://newsroom.ibm.com/2024-06-06-IBM-and-Pasqal-Initiate-Collaboration-to-Define-Classical-Quantum-Integration-for-Quantum-Centric-Supercomputers>

¹³ <https://iqcc.com/>

¹⁴ <https://pawsey.org.au/pioneering-room-temperature-quantum-computing-in-wa/>

¹⁵ <https://pawsey.org.au/apply/>

also pointed to Pawsey’s early adopter scheme for quantum, which supports researchers willing to engage in exploratory or integration work.

Managing hype of quantum capabilities and setting expectations:

One participant raised a concern about outreach programs potentially overhyping quantum computing. Pascal acknowledged this risk and shared how Pawsey's education efforts are deliberately framed. “We never try to promise that it will solve grand challenge problems trivially,” he said. Instead, the message is that quantum is a field of open questions and students might help answer them in the future.

3.5 Transforming R&D with advanced HPC and AI towards Quantum

Speaker: Naoyuki Isogai, Asia Regional Head for Cloud Solutions HPC/AI, Microsoft Corporation, Taiwan
2025, June 5

Naoyuki Isogai offered a practical overview of how Microsoft is advancing HPC and AI capabilities in the cloud, with a focus on accessibility, integration, and scientific utility.

A central theme of his talk was the role of cloud platforms in enabling broader access to advanced computational tools. He pointed to recent benchmarks showing Microsoft’s Azure based system ranking among the top three supercomputers globally (as listed in the biannual TOP500 list) in 2024¹⁶, using the same infrastructure that is publicly available to users. This, he argued, demonstrates how cloud systems can democratise access previously reserved for dedicated supercomputing centres.

He stressed that general purpose infrastructure alone isn’t sufficient for emerging scientific needs. Much like automotive users require different vehicles for different conditions, Naoyuki said researchers need computing environments that are tailored to specific workloads.

Naoyuki also shared real world examples where AI and HPC are being combined to accelerate discovery. One case involved identifying a new battery electrolyte in just 80 hours, a process that would traditionally take months if not years, by first using AI to filter 32 million candidates, followed by HPC simulations for validation¹⁷.

¹⁶ <https://top500.org/lists/top500/2024/06/>

¹⁷ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/blog/quantum/2024/01/09/unlocking-a-new-era-for-scientific-discovery-with-ai-how-microsofts-ai-screened-over-32-million-candidates-to-find-a-better-battery/>

To support research workflows, Microsoft has worked with hardware partners to optimise systems for cloud deployment.

Toward the end of his talk, Naoyuki pointed to the future. He noted that the intersection of HPC, AI, and quantum computing could unlock new capabilities in several scientific disciplines.

“Cloud is one of the most effective and efficient ways to democratise high-end computing resources. We’re purpose-building environments so that HPC and AI are truly accessible to everyone.”

- Naoyuki Isogai

Q&A with Naoyuki Isogai: Highlights

On the computing and power efficiency of quantum computing: Responding to a question about whether quantum computing is less power hungry than traditional HPC, the speaker cautioned against generalisations. He explained that with so many variations in quantum hardware design, power use must be evaluated in terms of performance per watt, rather than total consumption alone. The field is still too early in its evolution to make firm comparisons.

On cloud access and system reliability of quantum systems: The discussion also touched on the complexities of integrating quantum devices into cloud environments. While cloud platforms offer one of the most viable routes for remote access to quantum systems, the reliability of quantum hardware remains low compared to classical infrastructure. Devices often require calibration and may have uptimes as low as 20%, making seamless integration with high availability systems like HPC a continuing challenge.

On the role of cloud in democratising access to advanced computing: It was reiterated that cloud systems are playing a key role in making advanced computing more broadly accessible. By hosting high performance resources on public platforms, cloud providers can support research that would otherwise be limited to elite institutions. However, integrating newer quantum systems into that framework requires overcoming technical and architectural hurdles.

3.6 Quantum Horizons: Practical Progress and Future Directions

Speaker: Ujjwal Kumar, Principal Architect, Office of CTO, Microsoft Asia, Singapore
June 5, 2025

Ujjwal Kumar presented Microsoft's vision for hybrid quantum computing, combining cloud infrastructure, AI, HPC, and quantum systems to address real world scientific and industrial challenges. Similar to the previous speakers, he stressed that the power of quantum computing lies in its integration with traditional computing systems, especially in areas where probabilistic modelling and quantum effects provide a distinct advantage.

He pointed to chemistry and materials science as high impact domains, noting that 96% of manufactured goods depend on chemical processes. Quantum systems could enable more accurate simulations of electron level interactions, which are currently beyond the reach of classical machines, potentially accelerating breakthroughs in clean energy, drug discovery, and industrial chemistry.

To address these challenges, Microsoft has developed a hybrid computing model. High performance computing (HPC) manages large datasets; generative AI models, trained on chemistry libraries, streamline analysis; and quantum processors offer precision in candidate evaluation. This full stack approach is already accessible through Azure Quantum¹⁸, which supports platforms such as trapped ion, superconducting, and neutral atom systems. Notable recent milestones include Microsoft and Quantinuum successful creation and usage of 12 logical reliable qubits to perform a hybrid quantum chemistry simulation¹⁹.

Looking further ahead, Ujjwal introduced Microsoft's topological qubit development²⁰, a new approach designed for scalable, fault tolerant quantum computing. These qubits are built using custom engineered material known as a topoconductor, which creates a stable quantum state through the combination of semiconductors and superconductors at cryogenic temperatures. The company's 2024 release of the Majorana 1 chip marked the first physical implementation of this material²¹.

Ujjwal also cited evolving future application together with collaborations with DARPA²², the U.S. Air Force Research Laboratory, and Johns Hopkins University, focused on

¹⁸ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/solutions/quantum-computing>

¹⁹ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/blog/quantum/2024/09/10/microsoft-and-quantinuum-create-12-logical-qubits-and-demonstrate-a-hybrid-end-to-end-chemistry-simulation/>

²⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-024-08445-2>

²¹ <https://news.microsoft.com/source/features/innovation/microsofts-majorana-1-chip-carves-new-path-for-quantum-computing>

²² <https://www.darpa.mil/news/2025/quantum-computing-approaches>

developing utility scale quantum systems that can operate reliably across real world scientific workflows.

"If quantum can help us discover better catalysts, safer drugs, or cleaner fuels, then the societal impact is massive. That's the opportunity we're building toward."

- Ujjwal Kumar

Audience Q and A with Ujjwal Kumar: Highlights

On digital readout, measurements and system architecture: One participant asked whether the microwave bursts used to read quantum dots are processed within the quantum module or by a classical system. Kumar explained that the system is arranged in three layers: quantum hardware, a dedicated **measurement layer**, and a software interface. The measurement layer, featuring cryogenic control hardware, reads out quantum states digitally via classical electronics. Above that, a Software Development Kit (SDK) supports both low- and high-level languages. He stressed that bridging the quantum and digital domains is a key challenge in system development.

On hardware portability and API standards for quantum access: Another question covered whether there are evolving standards or APIs for accessing different quantum hardware types. Kumar pointed to the Quantum Intermediate Representation (QIR) Alliance²³, which Microsoft co-founded. QIR is a hardware agnostic intermediate language enabling interoperability across platforms like Qiskit²⁴ and Microsoft's SDK. Using QIR, developers can retarget code with minimal changes and use tools like resource estimation to optimise workflows before deployment.

Following the keynotes in each session, participants were divided into small groups for a moderated discussion on the key thematic areas of quantum applications, challenges towards the HPC Quantum transition, Skill development and policy considerable for global access. The following section describes the insights from these breakout groups.

²³ <https://github.com/qir-alliance>

²⁴ <https://www.ibm.com/quantum/qiskit>

4. Breakout Dialogues on HPC and Quantum: Insights into Applications, Barriers, Enablers, Skills and Policy

The roundtables brought together researchers, educators, policy leaders, and technologists to discuss the evolving terrain of quantum and HPC in interactive breakout sessions. Each session was framed around three guiding questions:

- Where might HPC and quantum computing have the most impact (current and future applications)?
- What are the biggest risks or blockers to inclusive adoption (challenges)?
- What would it take to make these technologies accessible, trusted, and ethically aligned (Skills, policy, and other enablers)?

We will present the key insights and shared themes derived from participant discussions across both roundtable sessions. While both sessions addressed the same three questions, each placed different emphasis on particular aspects. Below, we present insights from both sessions, along with cross-cutting themes that emerged across the discussions.

4.1 June 3 Breakout Sessions: Data, Cloud Access, Quantum skills, Security

This session spotlighted imaginative and practical applications of quantum across disciplines. Participants envisioned quantum being applied to AI, agriculture, climate modelling, and medical research. There was particular enthusiasm for using quantum to simulate complex social processes or run experiments not feasible with human subjects. One participant pointed to South Africa as an example of where cloud-based access to computing infrastructure might democratise advanced computing.

"Using cloud-based infrastructure could really help connect research institutions in parts of the world with limited local access. "

The discussion highlighted foundational challenges for these technologies, particularly around data quality and governance:

"Trust in any technology, from AI to quantum, begins with trusted data. Without reliable inputs, the outputs are inherently untrustworthy."

Concerns included biased datasets, incomplete metadata, lack of clear licensing, and unsustainable data migration practices. These were not abstract fears but practical blockers to trust in quantum enabled research.

When asked what would enable broader accessibility, participants pointed to the complex path of acquiring quantum skills:

"There's a steep learning curve and specialised infrastructure requirements for acquiring quantum skills. This is a systemic barrier."

To address this, the group called for quantum literacy efforts in schools, cloud-based learning environments, and simplified tools that support use without requiring deep technical expertise.

This session also tackled the security, policy, and governance implications of quantum adoption. Central to the discussion was the threat of RSA encryption²⁵ collapse, and the lack of institutional preparedness:

"Everything now that is encrypted is based on certain mathematical assumptions which a quantum computer will be able to solve... sensitive data could be decrypted in seconds."

While post quantum encryption and quantum key distribution (QKD) were cited as mitigations, participants worried about readiness gaps and geopolitical asymmetries. Several referenced European efforts like EuroQCI²⁶, but noted that progress is uneven globally:

"Europe, the US, China yes. But that leaves a big part of the globe unprepared."

The group also explored **licensing and data ownership** concerns. Participants warned that academic institutions lack sustainable data provision models, while AI companies extract value without accountability:

On the semantic side, there was widespread concern that **decades of work on metadata and data meaning** are being discarded in quantum and HPC infrastructures. Without sustained governance, participants feared that complexity and cost would reinforce inequality and reproduce the "ethics lag" seen in AI development.

²⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RSA_cryptosystem

²⁶ https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/connecting-europe-facility/about/quantum-communication-infrastructure-euroqci_en

4.2 June 5: High impact Use cases, Quantum readiness, Equity, Ethics

The discussions during the sessions covered several concrete quantum applications from ongoing or planned projects. One participant described a transport optimisation initiative where quantum methods are being trialled for timing of traffic signals and inferring vehicle flows on highways from limited data.

Another area of exploration is in quantum field simulations, especially for scientific domains like cosmology and early universe physics. These problems are particularly well suited to quantum approaches due to their natural alignment with quantum phase transitions. Beyond physics, quantum's potential was also highlighted for **machine learning tasks** where training data is scarce, but complexity is high, a common challenge in domains like healthcare:

"If you have 17 data points (on cancer diagnosis) ... and the 18th is the one you want to diagnose... Quantum techniques might pull out features a classical approach cannot."

Another participant working in climate modelling noted that while full production systems in climate science are unlikely to shift quickly to quantum, there is promise in machine learning integration for tasks like data gap filling or analysis efficiency.

Security was also a leading concern. Security was the leading concern. Participants repeatedly flagged the collapse of RSA encryption as a potential inflection point.

"Post-quantum protocols exist, but they're not quantum. They're classical algorithms that haven't yet been broken by quantum computers. And they're harder to implement."

There was a strong sense of institutional unreadiness for the transition. Participants stressed the logistical and financial costs of retooling encryption protocols across institutions.

Beyond security, the group explored issues of epistemic opacity and uncertainty, particularly in translating quantum level phenomena into reliable classical insights. Participants discussed the risks of misinterpreting quantum outputs in public or policy domains.

Usability surfaced as a critical cross cutting issue. Many participants acknowledged that full stack quantum programming is beyond the reach of most researchers.

This led to widespread endorsement of no code interfaces, reusable templates emphasising simplified, robust interfaces for equitable access.

“Researchers shouldn’t have to write Qiskit. They should be able to click a tool that lets them explore their science, not quantum mechanics.”

Participants noted that quantum computing holds clear promise for domains where classical computation hits natural limits, such as material science, chemistry, and molecular simulations.

“Classical computers, even supercomputers, can’t replicate how a molecule interacts at a quantum level... This is where quantum fits very well.”

There was agreement that **quantum enhanced simulation** is likely to be a leading use case but participants also stressed the **risk of premature hype** without adequate infrastructure, education, or policy frameworks.

Security was a dominant theme. One major risk flagged was the **“harvest now, decrypt later”** model, where actors collect encrypted datasets now, knowing that future quantum computers could break today's cryptographic schemes.

Several contributors noted the urgency of shifting to **post quantum cryptography**, with bodies like NIST and ETSI already producing standards. However, uptake is still limited, and **“crypto-agility”**, the ability to evolve encryption schemes over time remains underdeveloped in many institutions.

Another pressing concern was **scientific reproducibility** in quantum research. Access to a specific quantum computer may be time limited or geographically constrained, making it difficult to replicate experiments:

“What if you're using a completely different quantum computer and you can't reproduce your own results?”

This issue was tied to concerns about access asymmetries and the risk of creating a **“class system in research”**, where only elite institutions can afford meaningful engagement with these systems. The Pathways group provided a compelling snapshot of global disparities in digital infrastructure. One speaker, referencing experience from Southeast Asia, noted that entire regions lack reliable broadband, and that quantum computing access is “limited to a single lab” in some universities.

Others flagged that even in technologically advanced regions, rural communities lack basic mobile or internet coverage:

"You drive two hours out of a city in Western Australia in any direction and you're in a rural area without even mobile connection... Cloud access assumes connectivity which many simply don't have."

These concerns sparked calls for broader definitions of accessibility, encompassing not just API access or pricing, but also connectivity, curriculum inclusion, and institutional readiness.

The conversation closed with an impassioned argument for **early engagement with standards development**, both technical and regulatory. "If you don't engage, we'll go off and write something you then have to conform to... and you won't think it's right."

One contributor noted: "You shouldn't regulate what you don't yet fully understand, but we can't wait until it's too late either."

There was strong support for the formation of global communities of practice and interest groups to ensure underrepresented regions are not excluded from these foundational conversations.

"We're at the ground floor of quantum, which means we still have time to build it right. But only if everyone is in the room."

Participants repeatedly drew comparisons to AI, warning against letting history repeat itself. There was a shared concern that ethical reflection is once again lagging innovation.

"We failed to control AI early enough. Let's not make the same mistake with quantum."

The group discussed the dangers of elite capture, where a handful of powerful countries or corporations may come to dominate access and development. While cloud access might offer temporary solutions, it was seen as unsustainable and disempowering for less resourced regions. "Cloud creates dependency," one participant noted.

"With any power comes the risk of abuse. If we don't build ethical frameworks now, we're already too late."

Concerns included the possibility of quantum amplifying the harm already visible in AI, especially when used in sensitive domains like healthcare, law enforcement, or social services. The discussion also touched on the environmental footprint of quantum computing, highlighting that the infrastructure needed for cooling quantum machines could outweigh expected energy gains.

Cross cutting and Shared Themes

Despite varied contexts, participant roles, and disciplines, six consistent themes emerged across the breakout sessions as shown in the

Theme	Shared Insight
Real World Applications	Participants shared concrete use cases in traffic optimisation, chemical modelling, and climate forecasting, affirming quantum’s potential for near term relevance.
Data Governance & Trust	Data privacy, consent, metadata, and curation emerged as central. The lack of frameworks could derail progress.
Security & Standards	RSA decryption risk and the absence of agreed post quantum protocols prompted calls for inclusive standard setting.
Digital Divide	Infrastructure inequities were noted both between and within countries. Cloud access alone won’t solve this.
Skills & Usability	There is a need for intuitive, reliable, and trusted tools that allow domain researchers to engage with quantum.
Ethics & Public Good	Ethical readiness was seen as urgent. Participants advocated for early inclusion of ethicists and rights based design.

Table 1: Shared themes between the 3 June and 5 June roundtables during breakout discussions

5 Key Findings and Recommendations

In the following section, we present a set of 5 key findings and corresponding recommendations:

- Quantum computing delivers the greatest value when used alongside HPC and AI in hybrid workflows, enabling new breakthroughs in simulation, optimisation and scientific discovery.
- Cloud platforms are making advanced computing more accessible, but this must be matched with investment in connectivity, training and inclusive infrastructure.

- Quantum computing poses immediate risks to current encryption systems, requiring urgent adoption of quantum-safe standards and improved institutional readiness.
- Ethical frameworks must be embedded early through interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure equitable, transparent and accountable technology development.
- Addressing the global skills gap demands inclusive education, public-private partnerships, integrated training programmes and tools that lower entry barriers for researchers.

These findings and recommendations were distilled from the keynote speeches, extensive discussions held during the expert roundtables, breakout sessions, and interactive polls conducted via MentiMeter. To ensure robustness and accuracy, we cross checked these insights through a targeted literature review, drawing from current state of the art publications, recent industry developments, and global policy initiatives. We have elaborated them in the following paragraphs.

5.1 Better Together: The Quantum +HPC+AI Advantage

Quantum computing will achieve its greatest impact in tandem with classical HPC and AI, even in the short-term future. Experts were quick to dispel the misconception of quantum replacing classical supercomputers; instead, **quantum introduces new possibilities for problems that classical methods struggle with, while working alongside them**. The vision that emerged is one of *hybrid computing*: leveraging the respective strengths of each paradigm. Full stack approach couple be where **HPC manages large datasets, AI (especially machine learning) accelerates data analysis, and quantum processors provide precise solutions for specific sub problems**. By combining classical supercomputers, AI, and quantum, researchers can “work faster, scale better, and access cutting edge tools without traditional barriers. Moreover, AI itself is boosting classical HPC: t training AI surrogates on simulation data can drastically reduce runtime for complex problems, a strategy that could extend to quantum classical workflows. Embracing this convergence will require new software frameworks, co-designed algorithms, and cross-disciplinary teams, but it promises breakthroughs (in drug discovery, climate modelling, materials science and more) that neither quantum nor classical computing could achieve alone.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Invest in Hybrid Infrastructure:** Governments and research funders should support the development of **testbeds and pilot projects for quantum HPC**

integration. Supercomputing centers could be funded to install experimental quantum hardware onsite or in the cloud, connected directly to HPC systems.

- **Develop Unified Tools and Platforms:** The tech industry (cloud providers, software firms, open-source communities) should collaborate on building **user friendly platforms** that abstract the complexity of coordinating HPC, AI, and quantum resources. Researchers shouldn't need to be experts in all three domains to benefit from them. Initiatives could include middleware that manages workloads across CPUs, GPUs, and QPUs, as well as AI driven compilers that can decompose problems and dispatch tasks to the appropriate computing element.
- **Cross Domain Training and Research:** Academia and industry should cultivate talent and research programs that span quantum, AI, and HPC. These efforts must also incorporate domain-specific knowledge and social science perspectives to ensure responsible innovation that is both effective and socially relevant. For instance, universities might offer joint degree programs or certificates in Quantum Computing and Data Science and funding agencies can launch challenge grants for teams that include quantum physicists, computer scientists, and AI experts working together on societal problems (e.g. energy grid optimisation or pandemic modelling).

5.2 Democratising HPC and Quantum Infrastructure: Cloud a Key Enabler

Access to cutting edge computing be it supercomputers, massive AI models, or prototype quantum processors has historically been limited to well-funded labs and wealthy institutions. A key finding of the discussions is that **cloud computing platforms are transforming this landscape, helping to democratise access to advanced computing resources.** In fact, cloud offerings by major providers (e.g. AWS, Azure, IBM) already host quantum computers and high-end GPUs that anyone with an internet connection can use, often with free tiers for education, a scenario unthinkable a decade ago.

However, the discussions also raised critical caveats. **Democratisation is only meaningful if foundational inequalities are addressed.** Many communities lack the reliable internet connectivity that cloud services assume as one participant observed, “cloud access assumes connectivity which many simply don't have”. Moreover, simply providing access isn't enough if local researchers don't have the training to utilise it or if content is locked in certain languages. Thus, democratising advanced computing must go hand in hand with improving digital infrastructure, education, and inclusive outreach.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Close the Connectivity Gap:** Governments and development organisations should recognise internet and high-performance computing access as a matter of equity. This means investing in broadband infrastructure in underserved regions and research institutions and universities.
- **Cloud Credits and Shared Facilities:** To make cloud HPC/quantum accessible, stakeholders (industry, funders, NGOs) can provide cloud credit programs, grants, or sponsored accounts for researchers who lack resources.
- **Embed Training together with Cloud Access:** Cloud providers, both public and private, should provide training and shared access points to cloud resources.

5.3 Post quantum Security: No Time to Wait

Quantum computing poses a serious threat to existing cryptographic protections, and urgent action is required. Roundtable participants repeatedly highlighted the likely breakdown of RSA encryption as a major risk, pointing to a clear lack of institutional preparedness.

A key concern is the "harvest now, decrypt later" tactic, where attackers collect encrypted data today to decrypt once quantum capabilities emerge²⁷. Post quantum encryption technologies advancement and adoption has been slow and inconsistent.

Only a few major powers, including the US, China, and the EU, are advancing toward quantum safe communications. Most of the world remains vulnerable. To address this, NIST has released new quantum resistant algorithms and is urging organisations to begin transitioning now²⁸.

However, many lack crypto agility, the ability to quickly switch encryption methods which makes the shift costly and complex. Critical infrastructure, including AI and high-performance computing, faces similar risks and must be part of the solution.

Without coordinated global action, quantum advances could outstrip current defenses, threatening the security and integrity of digital systems. Preparing for post quantum security is not a future concern but a pressing strategic priority.

²⁷ <https://www.wired.com/story/q-day-apocalypse-quantum-computers-encryption/>

²⁸ <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2024/08/nist-releases-first-3-finalized-post-quantum-encryption-standards>

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Accelerate Standards and Adoption:** Policymakers and standards bodies should expedite the rollout of post quantum cryptography standards and mandate their adoption in government and critical infrastructure well before large scale quantum computers arrive.
- **Build Crypto Agility:** Organisations must assess their cryptographic dependencies and invest in crypto agility upgrading systems to quickly replace encryption schemes when needed. This includes updating hardware, software, and processes. Regular migration drills, similar to cybersecurity exercises, can help ensure readiness for a post quantum transition.
- **Global Inclusive Preparedness:** The global community should support resource limited countries and sectors in upgrading their security. A collaborative task force involving governments, academia, and industry could provide open-source tools, shared best practices, and funding. Initiatives like Europe’s EuroQCI should be expanded through international partnerships to avoid deepening the quantum security divide.

5.4 Ethics by Design: Proactive and Multi stakeholder Approach for Quantum & AI

As quantum computing and AI advance, stakeholders warned not to repeat the mistakes of past tech revolutions by letting ethics lag behind innovation. This entails embedding ethics and governance frameworks *now*, rather than retrofitting them after harm occurs. Indeed, concerns were raised that without clear governance, the complexity and cost of quantum/HPC systems could **reinforce inequality and reproduce the “ethics lag”**. Encouragingly, early efforts are underway: for example, the World Economic Forum’s **Quantum Computing Governance Principles**²⁹ lay out guidelines emphasising inclusiveness, security, transparency, and accountability in quantum innovation. Experts stress that governing emerging tech is not just a technical matter; it requires multidisciplinary collaboration. There were calls for quantum scientists to actively **“build bridges” with social scientists, ethicists, and policymakers** to jointly anticipate societal impacts. In short, ethics and governance must be treated as foundational design parameters for quantum, HPC, and AI systems.

²⁹ <https://www.weforum.org/publications/quantum-computing-governance-principles/>

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Embed Ethics in R&D Policy:** Policymakers should integrate ethical guidelines into national quantum and AI strategies from the outset. This could mean establishing ethics review boards for publicly funded quantum/HPC projects and requiring that proposals address societal impacts and risk mitigation plans.
- **Multi Stakeholder Innovation teams:** Research institutions and tech companies should create interdisciplinary “responsible innovation” teams for advancing quantum applications. These bodies would include quantum engineers, AI developers, ethicists, legal experts, and community representatives. Their role: to regularly evaluate projects for ethical and societal implications and ensure diverse perspectives (including from historically marginalised groups) inform design choices from the get go.
- **Global Governance Collaboration:** Given the borderless impact of these technologies, international organisations (UN, OECD, standards bodies) should facilitate forums for **shared governance**.

5.5. Bridging the Quantum and HPC Skills Gap through Education and Inclusion

A severe talent shortage in quantum and high-performance computing (HPC) threatens innovation and global technological advancement. In 2025, fewer than half of all quantum related job openings may be filled due to limited qualified personnel³⁰. Stakeholders in our roundtables highlighted significant barriers such as steep learning curves, limited hands-on infrastructure, and inadequate interdisciplinary skills connecting HPC, quantum, and AI. The issue is multi layered, from the foundational gaps in quantum literacy among STEM students to a critical shortage of specialists capable of bridging HPC and quantum fields. Without timely interventions, these skills deficit risks amplifying inequalities among institutions, restricting innovation to a privileged few. The STEM field already faces significant representation challenges, particularly with women and underprivileged groups. The highly specialised nature of HPC and Quantum skills may exacerbate this gap³¹.

³⁰ https://www.techmonitor.ai/hardware/quantum/quantum-computing-has-a-looming-skills-gap?utm_source=chatgpt.com

³¹ <https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20245/representation-of-demographic-groups-in-stem>

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Embed Quantum and HPC into Education Curricula:** Governments and academic institutions must integrate quantum computing and HPC fundamentals including the ethical aspects of these technologies into STEM curricula at primary and secondary levels. For instance, introducing high school modules on basic quantum algorithms and computational logic could cultivate early interest and understanding.
- **Expand Interdisciplinary Educational Programmes and Training:** Universities should offer specialised interdisciplinary programs merging HPC, AI, and quantum engineering. Industry internships, fellowships, and residency programs.
- **Prioritise Inclusion and Diversity Globally:** Deliberate, sustained efforts must be made to actively engage underrepresented communities in quantum and HPC fields worldwide. Programs like Australia’s “Quantum Girls” initiative, designed specifically to inspire and mentor young women should be scaled internationally and across marginalised groups.
- **Develop User Friendly Tools for Accessibility:** Research institutions and industry should invest in simplified, user friendly quantum computing interfaces and cloud based training sandboxes. This lowers entry barriers, enabling students and researchers to explore advanced computing capabilities without extensive prior expertise.

By proactively investing in inclusive education, targeted training, and accessible tools, we can significantly reduce the skills gap and build a diverse, vibrant quantum HPC workforce prepared to lead future innovations.

6. Final Reflection

Quantum computing is emerging as a powerful complement to HPC, not a replacement. Its near-term value lies in specific applications such as quantum chemistry, optimisation, and simulation, particularly when combined with AI and HPC in integrated workflows. This combination holds significant promise for accelerating scientific discovery.

At the same time, technical capability alone will not determine success. Gaps in infrastructure, education, equity, and governance must be addressed with the same urgency as hardware development. Access through the cloud may broaden availability, but without inclusive training, curriculum reform, and investment in connectivity, these opportunities will remain unevenly distributed.

To realise the opportunities and address the challenges ahead, we hope the insights in this white paper will support public and private infrastructure providers, research institutions, governments developing national quantum and HPC strategies, and funders aligning technical investment with social and ethical priorities to shape the future of research computing.

About the Research Data Alliance

The [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) was launched as a community driven initiative in 2013 with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and re use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society.

The RDA's mission is to build the social and technical bridges that enable that vision, accomplished through the creation, adoption and use of the social, organisational, and technical infrastructure needed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange. Scientists & researchers join forces with technical experts in focused Working Groups, exploratory Interest Groups and Communities of Practice. As of June 2025, the RDA is a 15000+ member strong community spread across the globe.

Everyone is welcome to join the RDA as an individual member free of charge. If you're interested in getting involved at the organisational level, please explore our [membership options](#).

About Microsoft

Microsoft Corporation is a multinational American technology company recognised for shaping the evolution of personal and enterprise computing. Founded in 1975 and headquartered in Redmond, Washington, the company initially revolutionised software accessibility through its early operating systems. Over the decades, Microsoft expanded its portfolio to encompass a broad spectrum of technologies, including productivity

software, cloud infrastructure, gaming, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing. With a longstanding emphasis on innovation and digital transformation, Microsoft continues to play a pivotal role in defining the future of the tech industry.

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Disclaimer: This white paper is a collaborative effort between the Research Data Alliance and Microsoft, with contributions from participants of both organisations who did not receive any compensation for their involvement. AI tools were used as writing assistance for editing, language refinement, and coding support during the preparation of this document. All quotes and statements attributed to speakers and participants have been directly verified using transcripts and video recordings. Attribution has been made only with explicit consent, and general discussion quotes, although anonymised, have also been validated against recordings. Attributed quotes were shared with their respective speakers for review and commentary prior to publication. Graphs included in this paper were generated by the author, while other graphics were provided by the speakers, all of which have been cleared for use. Any substantial claims presented in this paper are supported by expert speaker statements as well as footnote citations from referenced sources, all verified by the author.

Annex A: Keynote Speaker Bios

Torsten Bloth, HPC and AI Black Belt EMEA, Microsoft, Berlin, Germany

Torsten's extensive background in High Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) positions him as a key player in the technological advancement of these fields. His role at Microsoft, focusing on complex sales strategies for emerging technologies, showcases his ability to navigate and grow in rapidly evolving markets. With a career spanning over 20 years, including significant roles at IBM, Lenovo, and AWS, Torsten brings a wealth of knowledge and experience to his current position. His expertise in scalable applications and cloud technologies is crucial for developing solutions that meet the demanding computational needs of diverse industries, from automotive to public sector research and development.

Pascal Elahi, Quantum Supercomputing Lead, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, Perth, Australia

Dr. Pascal Jahan Elahi is a quantum and high-performance computing expert who leads the quantum supercomputing research group at the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre. With a PhD in computational astrophysics, he has a strong background in developing astronomical software for HPC systems. Now deeply involved in the HPC community, Pascal supports researchers across disciplines, ranging from astronomy to clinical health, in scaling their workflows to supercomputers. He collaborates with the Australian astronomical community and pioneers the integration of ML and AI into HPC for new scientific domains. Pascal's current focus lies at the intersection

of quantum computing and supercomputing. He and his team work to grow Australia's quantum research ecosystem by providing access to quantum systems, training, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. A passionate STEM educator and advocate for diversity in HPC, Pascal also creates training materials for researchers and introduces quantum computing and STEM to students at all levels.

Naoyuki Isogai, Asia Regional Head for Cloud Solutions HPC/AI, Microsoft Corporation, Taiwan

Naoyuki leads the solution and team for Azure cloud across Australia & New Zealand, Greater China Region, Japan, Korea, India, and Southeast Asia, to enable HPC/AI solutions for key industries such as Automotive/Manufacturing, Energy, Finance Services, Life Science, and Public Sector, through strategic partnerships with global and regional solution providers. Out of his 25 years' career at Microsoft, Naoyuki has wide variety of business coverages from clouds such as Azure to clients such as Windows, engineering tools such as Visual Studio to end user tools such as Office, and even consumer products such as Xbox. Currently Naoyuki is based in Taiwan with his

family after moving from Japan back in the year of 2016.

Mikael Johansson, Manager, Quantum Technologies, CSC, Espoo, Finland

In his role as Manager for Quantum Technologies at CSC, The Finnish IT Center for Science, Dr. Johansson oversees CSC's participation in global initiatives related to quantum technologies, and in general explores and enables the uptake of quantum tech in RDI communities. He considers quantum accelerated high performance computing to be a central part of future supercomputing ecosystems. He spent twenty years in academia, studying and teaching quantum mechanical effects in (bio)chemistry. Dr Johansson holds an associate professorship in physical chemistry at the University of Helsinki, is director of the Finnish Quantum Computing Infrastructure, co-founder of the Nordic Estonian quantum computing infrastructure initiative NordiQuEst, and deputy

director of the EuroHPC LUMI-Q quantum computing effort. He considers collaboration across the globe to be a highly synergistic endeavour, especially when it comes to quantum technologies.

Ujjwal Kumar, Principal Architect, Office of CTO, Microsoft Asia, Singapore

Ujjwal Kumar is a Principal Architect in the Office of CTO, Microsoft Asia, specializing in AI, Agentic AI, Quantum Computing, and Quantum Safe technologies. With 22 years of experience across diverse industries, he collaborates with strategic customers to drive digital transformation. Ujjwal co leads Microsoft's internal, global Quantum Computing community and is an Azure Quantum ambassador & Quantum Safe ambassador lead.

Sabina Leonelli, Professor of Philosophy of Technology, Technische Universität München, Germany

Prof. Sabina Leonelli is a leading philosopher of science specialising in data governance, AI, and emerging technologies like quantum computing. Currently Chair of Philosophy and History of Science and Technology at the Technical University of Munich, she co directs the Ethical Data Initiative and the TUM Public Science Lab, as well as the Open Science Studies research group. Her work critically examines how data intensive practices shape knowledge production, particularly in the life sciences and digital research infrastructures. Leonelli advises major institutions including the European Commission and the Italian National Centre for Big Data, High Performance, and Quantum Computing on responsible data use and Open Science policy.

Annex B: Contributing Participants

We sincerely thank all participants for their enthusiasm, expertise, and valuable contributions during the roundtable discussions. Their insights have been instrumental in shaping the findings of this whitepaper.

Please note that only those participants who provided explicit consent have been acknowledged in the list of contributors.

2025, June 3 Session Contributors

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
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Liseanne	Cadieux	Lead Data Architect	Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance)	Canada
Avinash	Kumar	Quantum Ambassador	Microsoft	UK
H.J.(Jelle)	Treep	Coordinator Computing Support team	Utrecht University	Netherlands
Liza	Malinina	Data Engineer II	Microsoft	Estonia
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Rachel	Chiang	Product Marketing Manager	Microsoft	US
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Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
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Kavana	D Rajan	Support Engineer	Microsoft	India
Siyabonga	Peter	Network Engineer	CSIR	South Africa
Amy	Nurnberger	Program Head, Data Management Services	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	US
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Rosie	Allison	Communication Specialist	RDA	Belgium

2025, June 5 Session Contributors

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Pascal	Elahi	Quantum Supercomputing Lead	Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre	Australia
Michelle	Barker	Director	ReSA	Australia
Emily	Barker	Senior High Performance Computing Engineer	University of Western Australia	Australia
Naoyuki	Isogai	Asia Regional Head for Cloud Solutions HPC/AI	Microsoft	Taiwan
Moji	Ghadimi	Head of AI and Quantum Algorithms	QCIF	Australia
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Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Ujjwal	Kumar	Principal Architect, Office of CTO	Microsoft Asia	Singapore
Ruchipas	Bavontaweepanya	Lecturer	Thammasat University	Thailand
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Connie	Clare	Community Development Manager	RDA	United Kingdom
Shalini	Kurapati	Community Engagement (RDA)/ Co founder (Clearbox)	RDA/ Clearbox AI	Italy
Rosie	Allison	Communication Specialist	RDA	Belgium
Hilary	Hanahoe	Secretary General	RDA	Italy
Trish	Radotic	RDA Regional Community Manager	Australian Research Data Commons / Research Data Alliance	Australia

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